

THE THEORETICAL STUDY FOR IMPLEMENTING CBI IN TEACHING ESP IN VIETNAM

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ABSTRACT

The article is an attempt to present briefly the effective Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) for English for Specific purposes (ESP) classes. The author has articulated the shared understanding of methodological practice found for learning and teaching of both content and language. This article is trying to develop the widely-accepted term Content-based Instruction (CBI), CLIL in teaching ESP and give a clear-cut implementation in teaching ESP for university students in Vietnam.

TÓM TẮT

Bài viết trình bày ngắn gọn nội dung của ứng dụng Phương pháp Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) cho các lớp học Anh văn chuyên ngành (ESP). Tác giả đã làm rõ các phương pháp luận liên quan đến Nội dung chuyên ngành và phương pháp dạy học Ngoại ngữ. Bài viết này góp phần phân tích triển các thuật ngữ mới liên quan đến Content-based Instruction (CBI), CLIL trong việc giảng dạy ESP và đưa ra các ứng dụng thực tế trong việc giảng dạy ESP cho sinh viên đại học ở Việt Nam.

1. Introduction

There are many views on the definitions of the Content-Based Instruction (CBI) because language learners and teachers have been working on with others approaches and methodologies rather than the term CBI. It is only acknowledged when a key step in designing an effective curriculum that meets the needs of students, the instructors and specific programs in order to identify and agree on a working definition of these terms. It is very important to classify the concept of 'content' in CBI. Crandall and Tucker (1990) describe *content* as "academic subject matter" while Curtain and Pesola (1994) express CBI as "curriculum concepts being taught through the foreign language". These discrete views represent a contrasting aspect of CBI in which 'content' itself is emphasized in a language learning context.

The tendency of applying academic content-based courses into English language programs at Vietnam university have been known as courses of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) where there is an

emphasis on the second language acquisition in specialized contexts, occupational needs, and assessment. Language teachers have developed ESP areas into subdivisions such as English for Academic Purposes (EAP), English for Strategic Purposes (ESTP), English for Financial Purposes (EFP), Business English (ESB), Nursing English (NE), Flight Attendant English (FAE), Hotel Industry English (HIE), English Legal (EL), Tourism English (TE), English for Accounting (EFA) and many others. It is clear that language teachers traditionally practice their teaching with an understanding the belief that language proficiency is achieved through learning of structures, vocabulary in isolation, but now there has been a shift of the focus in which language proficiency is believed to be achieved through the study of subject matter (Stryker & Leaver, 1997:15).

Therefore, many teachers have a need to know how to teach language courses that are considered as content-based curriculum. This paper will address the basic steps for teaching a content-based curriculum for a university-level EFL

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classroom effectively.

2. The Content Based Instruction studies

CBI has been used in a variety of language learning contexts for the last 25 years in the Western world but, in Vietnam, its popularity and wider applicability have attracted a lot for nearly 15 years. CBI is geared to stimulate students to think and learn through the use of the target language. Such an approach lends itself quite naturally to the integrated teaching of the four traditional language skills. In this approach, Brinton states that students are exposed to study skills and learn a variety of language skills which prepare them for the range of academic tasks they will encounter. Also, researches in second language acquisition offer additional support for CBI.

2.1 What is CBI?

There are many views about CBI, but one of the most influential definitions is “*a teaching method that emphasizes learning about something rather than learning about language*”. This interest of this concept has now spread to EFL classrooms around the world where teachers are

discovering that their students like CBI and are excited to learn English this way. In 2001, Richards & Rodgers defines CBI as “*an approach to second language teaching in which teaching is organized around the content or information that students will acquire, rather than around a linguistic or other type of syllabus*” (Richards & Rodgers, 2001, p.204). In other words, CBI involves integrating the learning of language with the learning of content simultaneously; here, content typically means academic subject matter such as math, science, or social studies.

2.2 The models of CBI

Depending on a multiplicity of factors such as educational setting, level, and the nature of instruction, The CBI models are either implemented in foreign language settings or are more typically applied in second language contexts. For each kind of the models, programs and approaches, students engage in some way with content using a non-native language. The instructional experiences in which students engage may be placed on the continuum below.

Content-Driven				Language-Driven	
<i>Total Immersion</i>	<i>Partial Immersion</i>	<i>Sheltered Courses</i>	<i>Adjunct Model</i>	<i>Theme-Based Courses</i>	<i>Language classes with frequent use of content for language practice</i>

Figure 1: Content-based language teaching: a continuum of content and language Integration. Met (1999:7)

Brinton, Snow, and Wesche (1989) describe three basic approaches to language and content integration in post-secondary settings: sheltered courses, adjunct courses, and theme-based courses.

2.2.1 The sheltered model

Sheltered courses are subject courses taught in the L2 using linguistically sensitive teaching strategies in order to make content accessible to learners who have less than native-like proficiency. Sheltered courses are content-driven: the goal is for students to master content;

students are evaluated in terms of content learning, and language learning is secondary. This model is best applied for the ESL environment.

2.2.2 The Adjunct model

In contrast, in the adjunct model of language/content integration, both language and content are the goal. Adjunct courses lie at the center of the continuum of content/language integration. Students are expected to learn content material while simultaneously acquiring academic language proficiency. Content instructors and language instructors share responsibility for student learning, with students evaluated by content instructors for subject matter mastery, and by language instructors for 'language skills. Unlike sheltered courses, where students are all learning content in an L2, in the adjunct model content classes may be comprised of both L1 and L2 content learners, but language instruction is almost always for L2 learners.

2.2.3 The theme based model

To the right of adjunct courses on the continuum are theme-based courses. Theme-based courses are language-driven: the goal of these courses is to help students develop L2 skills and proficiency. Themes are selected based on their potential to contribute to the learner's language growth in specific topical or functional domains. Unlike sheltered courses, which are taught by content instructors, and adjunct courses that are co-taught, theme-based courses are taught by language instructors to L2 Learners who are evaluated in terms of their language growth. Students (and their teachers) are not necessarily accountable for content mastery. Indeed, content learning is incidental. Each of these

approaches is discussed in more detail below.

2.3 Why CBI?

Duruy pointed out a lot of evidences in which CBI has its advantages than the others approaches in language learning and teaching. He claimed that

(. . .) a second language is most successfully acquired when the conditions mirror those present in first language acquisition, that is, when the focus of instruction is on meaning rather than on form; when the language input is at or just above the competence of the student, and when there is sufficient opportunity for students to engage in meaningful use of that language in a relatively anxiety-free environment.

Dupuy (2000: 206)

A major source of support for CBI derives from the work of some researchers in the area of second language acquisition (SLA), particularly from the principles of Krashen and Swain. The theories of Krashen (1984) claim that SLA occurs when the learner receives comprehensible input (what he called "i + 1"), not when he or she is forced to memorize vocabulary or manipulate language by means of batteries of grammar exercises. CBI principles are closely related to the hypothesis, as the focus of instruction is on the subject matter, and not on the form or, in Krashen's words, it is on "what is being said rather than how" (Krashen, 1984: 62). In the other words, CBI is increasingly important in curriculum development for SLA, as language and non-language departments in universities are finding the integration of core-content as part of the second language curriculum to be beneficial. CBI focuses on language learning and content learning (Stoller, 2004). Moreover, Grabe and Stoller (1997)

describe the benefits of a CBI approach to student learning. For example, students receive increased opportunities to enhance their knowledge and understanding of core-content in tandem with language learning activities that are based on core-content. This, in turn, stimulates and supports their second language and interpersonal communication skills acquisition.

2.4 A brief conclusion

As I have been stated in this part, CBI is not so much a revolutionary proposal for language teaching as a new orientation with the global trends. The benefits of the approach are supported by both extensive research on theoretical foundations and the outcomes reported by numerous designers and implementers of successful experiences in a multiplicity of settings, institutions and levels of instruction. There also exists a set of well-documented standard models specifically developed to fulfill the particular needs and demands of different groups, settings and educational purposes. Moreover, as has been detailed, CBI crosses over disciplines and thematic spheres, providing a flexible teaching framework with optimal scope for the accommodation of the most diverse content areas. The production and execution of a CBI course or program potentially constitutes a most stimulating challenge for language teachers, as the materialization of the real academic, cognitive and even personal interests and demands of both lecturers and learners can be accomplished by means of this methodological framework.

3. The real instructions for applying CBI in teaching ESP at HUFU

3.1 Content Vocabulary Instruction

More often than not, the students haven't been exposed to the English vocabulary and concepts necessary for comprehending content area material, and teachers tend to draw from materials that represent accounting major. Lesson design and delivery must help students to understand English words in the context of lesson. For example, students who have never heard about accounting terms about financial reports, let students have firsthand experience with the real financial reports, so they may better understanding of the concept.

If the students learn words out of context, such as from a list of dictionary definitions, is very difficult for students, words and concepts can easily be misconstrued in ways that are not at all related to the intended meaning. When students memorize the meanings of words on a specific subject matter list, they may not be able to use the words in their own writing or verbal production.

Another way of understanding context clues, such as embedded definitions, pictures, charts, and tables, helps students build the blocks (schema) that they will need to comprehend the text. Let's take an example of T-account that consists of date, explanation, accredit and debit. If the students look at the form of T-account (*see figure 2*) they may understand the term T-account.

Figure 2: the demonstration of T-account

3.2 Content Writing Instruction

Writing is a particularly challenging language domain for students to master, perhaps due to the lack of intensity and intentionality that we devote to it. The ability to learn English in Accounting means that students must be able to write in English in their subject-matter topics. Learning to write involves being able to communicate and convey ideas meaningfully through the real practice in their professional job such as defining an item into an account in a journal of bookkeeping. It was critically important for teachers to model and conduct a think-aloud about the summary-writing process, as well as to engage him in practicing the process. The teacher should teach writing in all content chapters before exposing students to creative writing or the teacher should encourage students to share their writing with classmates. Students can display work in the classroom on the wide papers in the classrooms. Writing is an essential component of learning English and requires instruction that is matched to each student stage of English language acquisition. Homework and assessment must also be targeted to the English learning levels of students.

3.3 Reading Comprehension Instruction

Teachers should teach students the exact language that they will need to talk about what they have read. It is highly

motivating to essentially tell students, “This is what good readers do, and now you are going to learn how to do it, too.” English language learners also reap the benefits of participating in whole-class instruction while also individually practicing with books that are suitable for their levels of English language acquisition (*Reading workshop’s ideas*). The teacher has let students follow what Menzella (1991) defines as six reading comprehension strategies:

1. Visualizing what is happening in the content,
2. Activating background knowledge by making connections,
3. Asking mental questions to self-check comprehension,
4. Learning how to make inferences about what is read,
5. Determining the importance of information in a text, and
6. Synthesizing information that is learned.

The advantage of these instructions is that language environment is immersed in the target language. The six essential reading comprehension strategies should be taught to students in all grade levels. The teacher should how to teach students to visualize what is happening in the text, activate background knowledge by making connections, ask mental questions to self-check comprehension, learn how to draw inferences from the text, determine the

importance of information in the text, and synthesize the information. By using these strategies, teachers can help students to become better readers.

4. Discussion and Implication

Second language acquisition is enhanced by comprehensible input (Krashen, 1982, 1985), which is a key pedagogical technique in content-based instruction, and natural language cannot be learned without meaning. Therefore, CBI should be phased in and adapted to suit different language environments so as to yield benefits for learners. The essay is going to present several suggestions and implications that may hopefully contribute to the development of language teaching in EFL classes in Vietnam.

Content and language are balanced in terms of priority at this level. Authentic materials are inevitable and tasks must be related to real life knowledge. The content is not necessarily new to students, and it must be related to students' background. The aim of language class is to help students read and write reports, research, or else in English, not to learn any new concepts or information in the language classes.

Teachers implementing CBI should have their own choice of selecting materials and evaluation as long as they meet the requirements set forth by the department or school. Tests and exams are not written for all students, but rather teachers in each particular class are responsible for the classes he/she is in charge.

Students' need analysis should be carried out as frequently as possible to meet their demands; students will find it more interesting to study a language in which they can revise what they have

learnt in term of content, i.e. subject matter, or at least learn something new.

Relevant materials will partly contribute to the concept of comprehensible input that may foster the rate of acquisition in language learners.

5. Conclusion

According to Swain (1980), the research on content-based language learning has revealed positive impacts on language acquisition if it is supported by the use of appropriate materials. Obviously, content in efficient CBI includes not only appropriate materials brought into the class, but also meaningful and suitable topics carefully chosen by the teachers. The essay has attempted to present the concept of CBI, or rather the philosophy of teaching content via a second language, with a hope of fostering the development of language acquisition in learners. The paper has not fully expressed issues or problems that may emerge from implementing CBI in classrooms in Vietnam. The paper has, however, explicitly demonstrated that CBI is a need and should be phased in. One of the big shortcomings of this research is that the author does not present and focus on the testing the effectiveness of adopting CBI in teaching ESP for University level students. This point of view will be presented in the term of another research about the implementation of CBI. It is my responsibility to keep track of the implementation and will further express, discuss, and analyze more thoroughly the feasibility of applying and adapting CBI in language classes in Vietnam. Hopefully, the essay has been a kind of food for thought for readers and teachers to look forwards the approaches and methodology for teaching ESP course.

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